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REPORT

Implementation of PI-LIST at ISOLDE

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Abstract

The Perpendicularly Illuminated Laser Ion Source and Trap, PI-LIST, was implemented at ISOLDE as a novel ion source for high resolution in-source laser spectroscopy applications and enhanced isomer-pure radioactive ion beam production. Requirements in terms of experimentally achievable linewidths of below 1 GHz and efficiency comparable to standard LIST operation are met. The unit enabled the first nuclear structure study of neutron-rich actinium isotopes at ISOLDE, of particular interest due to the expected emergence of octupole deformed nuclei in this area of the nuclear chart.

LISA ITN, 2020

For more information on the project, partners and contributors please see: lisa-itn.web.cern.ch

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Executive Summary:

On-line in-source laser spectroscopy is limited in resolution by Doppler broadening in the high temperature environment (typically 2000 C) required for isotope volatilization. A way to overcome this limitation within the ion source unit is to employ perpendicular laser illumination of the effusing atom beam, meaning that only the transverse velocity spread contributes to the Doppler broadening of the spectral line. This is at least an order of magnitude lower than that of the longitudinal velocity spread. The concept was employed in the PI-LIST ion source at JGU Mainz, where it became the principal technique of high-resolution laser spectroscopy, where also an adaption for on-line facility applicability was developed and tested. The scope of this work was to implement and validate this unit at ISOLDE.

Required infrastructure modifications included a design change of the extraction electrode to allow off-center laser passing. Systematic tests confirmed this alteration does not compromise ion beam quality. Single ion counting detection capabilities were installed not only for enabling measurements of low-yield isotopes but also to validate operation modes by distinct time structure features, and vice-versa aiding in data recording and filtering.

The goal of highly Doppler-reduced resolution in the new ion source was demonstrated on actinium with an experimental linewidth of around 200 MHz, as opposed to 1.55 GHz in standard RILIS configuration. This achievement enabled a successful ISOLDE on-line experiment on neutron-rich actinium isotopes.

These results, validating the new in-source high-resolution capabilities at ISOLDE, have already triggered multiple dedicated experiment proposals within the LISA network and beyond in the ISOLDE user community.

1. INTRODUCTION

On-line in-source laser resonance ionization has been proven to be a highly sensitive tool for nuclear structure investigations on isotopes with low production and extraction yields [1],[2]. While the efficiency of this technique is unrivalled, the spectral resolution is ultimately limited by Doppler broadening in the hot cavity required to ensure atom volatilization. At typical operation temperatures around 2000 °C, depending on transition wavelength and atomic mass, this leads to a 1-10 GHz experimental resolution limit, whereas precise measurements of nuclear magnetic and quadrupole moments often require resolving hyperfine structure (HFS) splitting significantly below the GHz regime [3]. Additionally, HFS resolution capabilities would help to discriminate ionization of different nuclear isomers ,.

A new laser ion source design has been proposed to provide in-source spectroscopy capabilities down to experimental linewidths of 100 – 200 MHz, an order of magnitude below usual limitations. It is based on the high beam purity Laser Ion Source and Trap (LIST) [4], [5]: laser ionization takes place in a radiofrequency quadrupole (RFQ) structure directly downstream the hot cavity, while potential contamination due to non-laser related ionization mechanisms in the latter is electrostatically blocked. In the new so-called Perpendicularly Illumination LIST (PI-LIST) mode [6], a crossed laser / atom beam geometry reduces the experimentally observed Doppler broadening by addressing only the transversal velocity components of the effusing atom ensemble.

In recent years, this method was employed very successfully at off-line experiments at JGU Mainz for nuclear structure investigations on long-lived radioactive isotopes [7], [8], where it became the principal method for high-resolution laser spectroscopy. In Mainz, the transversal laser is introduced through a window in the vacuum vessel directly at the ion source location. At on-line facilities such as ISOLDE, where radioisotope production in a target directly coupled to this ion source results in an inaccessible and highly radioactive environment, this approach is not technically feasible.

A respective adaption of the PI-LIST structure to circumvent this limitation and provide on-line suitability was developed at JGU Mainz [9]: The spectroscopy laser beam is guided off-center through the beam line in parallel to the ionization lasers, and then deflected perpendicularly by metal surfaces directly downstream the hot cavity orifice, inside the LIST RFQ structure (see fig. 1). Off-line hyperfine structure experiments on holmium isotopes confirmed the applicability of this technique in direct comparison with the window setup, and benchmark tests on rubidium demonstrated resolution capabilities down to significantly below 100 MHz [9], [10].

Fig. 1: On-line applicable version of the Perpendicularly Illuminated Laser Ion Source and Trap PI-LIST. The narrow-bandwidth spectroscopy laser is guided off-center through the beam line and deflected perpendicularly just at the entrance of the RFQ structure, where the density of the effusing atom beam from the hot cavity is highest. As this laser only addresses velocity classes in its propagation direction, the Doppler broadening is greatly reduced in comparison to probing the longitudinal direction of the hot vapor cloud. Figure taken from [9].

The scope of deliverable D2.2 was to implement this ion source at ISOLDE. Within WP2 (“Novel techniques and technologies for actinide research”), it paves the way to investigate actinide elements and especially the neutron-rich actinium isotopes in the region of assumed octupole deformation, relevant to recent Energy Density Functional theories incorporating reflection symmetry breaking [11]. As such, this work follows the efforts of actinium nuclear structure investigations with different high-resolution techniques such as in-gas-jet laser spectroscopy on neutron-deficient isotopes [12] all employing tailor-made high-resolution laser technology also developed in the framework of LISA.

2. TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PI-LIST AT ISOLDE

2.1. PREREQUISITES

The implementation of the ISOLDE PI-LIST is based on the existing infrastructure to run a “standard” LIST for high purity ion beam production, and the groundwork performed off-line at JGU Mainz.

An obstacle to overcome is to provide line-of-sight for an off-center laser beam to propagate 10-15 meters from the Resonance Ionization Laser Ion Source (RILIS) laser system through the ion beam vacuum vessel up to the reflecting mirrors. This path is obstructed by the ion beam extraction electrode right in front of the target/ion source unit. The effect of any physical alteration of this element in terms of changes in extracted ion beam properties such as shape or emittance needed to be evaluated. Additionally, the displacement of the laser beams on the entrance window at the separator magnet section when changing to perpendicular illumination had to be verified.

In order to provide a versatile system for ion beam production and laser spectroscopy over the complete RILIS-available range of elements, the performance of the reflecting metal mirror surfaces for different wavelengths needed to be investigated. Significant losses would influence the required laser power levels.

Lastly, a detector system capable of resolving the ion bunch time structure imprinted by the 10 kHz pulsed laser system had been shown in the past to provide an extremely valuable diagnostics tool for verification of operation modes. The ion bunch time structure is greatly reduced if ionization only happens in the very confined space just behind the repelling electrodes, whereas collinear illumination all along the central LIST axis produces a broader structure.

2.2. IMPLEMENTATION AND VERIFICATION

Following previous ion trajectory simulation work [9], the addition of four symmetrically placed orifices on the rim of the standard ISOLDE extraction electrode was chosen as solution to enable passage of an off-center laser beam without compromising ion beam quality (see fig. 2a). A back-to-back comparison (identical target/ion source unit and operation parameters) between a frontend setup with the standard electrode, and the adapted one was conducted directly at the ISOLDE GPS separator. Extracted ion beam intensities, beam shape (see fig. 2b) and tunability tests towards the far end of the ISOLDE beam line were, confirming no apparent change of ion beam characteristics and thus transparency of the design change for standard ISOLDE operation.

Fig. 2: a) Adapted extraction electrode to allow off-center laser guidance, installed at ISOLDE frontend. b) Ion beam scanner results (H: horizontal, V: vertical) from back-to-back comparison of standard electrode (without side orifices, dashed lines) and modified electrode (solid lines). Negligible influence on ion beam characteristics is demonstrated.

Line of sight of all possible laser beam paths on both ISOLDE frontend stations was examined with a specialised ISOLDE target unit hosting a large aperture laser power sensor inside. By changing laser pointing in the RILIS cabin into the different directions and recording the measured power in comparison to the one measured in central configuration, possible obstructions by the edge of the separator entrance window were quantified. All possible accesses from the individual laser beam paths to each offset direction were documented.

The plain polished stainless-steel surfaces to reflect the laser beams were tested with available laser beams of different wavelengths in a test setup. Reflectivity of 55 % and 52 % was measured for wavelengths of 395 nm and 760 nm, respectively. For the UV wavelength of 302 nm a decreased efficiency of 35% occurred. These values are more than sufficient to perform narrow-bandwidth spectroscopy, where the laser power of the respective transition under investigation typically must be attenuated to the mW regime or below, whereas available laser output power is at least in the order of some 10 mW even for technically more demanding wavelength production. Significant alteration of beam shape quality was not observed, especially not over the comparable short distance after reflection. If enhanced reflectivity is demanded, different metal coatings could be applied, with greater than 80 % reflectivity, e.g., with silver coatings have been shown to work [9].

In order to provide time-resolved data acquisition of the produced ion bunches, in collaboration with other LISA-related experiments at ISOLDE, a single ion counting-capable detector (ETP MagneTOF mini model 14925) was purchased and prepared to be used at different locations in the beam line. Time-tagging counting hardware and respective histogram software was implemented based on the CRIS experiment data acquisition. Besides ion bunch investigations, the availability of a single ion sensitive detector alone (superior sensitivity to the ISOLDE standard Faraday Cup devices, which are applicable for ion current measurements above $\sim 10\text{fA}$ or $\sim 100,000$ ions per second) already enhances experimental possibilities and was employed for multiple campaigns.

The ion bunch time structures were measured during a test run on titanium ions with this detector for the different operation modes of collinear laser illumination (standard-LIST) and perpendicular illumination (PI-LIST), the results are shown in Fig. 3. Indeed, switching of the laser guidance to perpendicular mode manifested itself in the disappearance of the various well-understood features of ion creation in standard LIST mode [5]. The only remaining peak represents ions which are created directly downstream of the repelling electrodes, at the location of the laser intersection. Besides this confirmation of the operation mode, dedicated time-gating techniques (either by software, or by fast laser-synchronized ion beam deflection) can thus additionally be applied. Further suppression of any signal that is not created by laser

impact (non-suppressed contamination or detector background) is possible, as well as remnants of diffusely reflected laser light that does not incline on the correct perpendicular pathway.

Fig. 3: Ion bunch time structure in standard collinear laser illumination with all lasers (LIST mode) and perpendicular illumination of one laser (PI-LIST mode) at 10 kHz laser repetition rate. It is apparent that all features besides a narrow bunch disappear, which proves that ionization solely takes place at a distinct location just behind the repelling electrodes where the laser beams intersect.

3. SPECTROSCOPICAL RESULTS

In order to exploit the capacity of the low-Doppler laser / atom interaction, a suitable narrow-bandwidth laser is needed. An injection-seeded, stabilized ring cavity was used to provide Fourier-limited pulsed laser light [13] of ~ 20 MHz bandwidth in fundamental output. The cavity was seeded by a commercial Sirah Matisse Ti:sapphire cw laser provided by the CRIS experiment in a setup described in [10].

High resolution tests and experiments were conducted on actinium, using the well-established ground state transition at 438.58 nm that was employed in all previous experiments [12], [11], followed by excitation into an auto-ionizing state by 424.69 nm light. Correspondingly, the output of the ring laser was frequency-doubled, yielding an expected bandwidth of ~ 30 MHz.

Fig. 4 shows a scan of the highest energy singlet peak within the hyperfine structure pattern for ^{227}Ac , which due to its high production rate and off-line availability with a half-life of 22 years was chosen as the reference isotope. Laser and ion source parameters were optimized for the best achievable resolution, i.e., the laser power was reduced well below saturation, and laser pulse delay techniques [14] were employed at cost of efficiency. The resulting experimental linewidth of slightly above 200 MHz clearly is way below the corresponding Doppler width in the hot cavity at identical working parameters (2000 °C heating to ensure proper volatilization) can be calculated as 1.55 GHz. Thus, the operation of the PI-LIST at ISOLDE for high-resolution spectroscopy is ultimately confirmed.

Fig. 4: Single resonance in the hyperfine structure of the 439 nm ground state transition in actinium, recorded with optimized parameters for resolution in PI-LIST mode at ISOLDE. The experimental linewidth of slightly above 200 MHz clearly shows the outperformance of the Doppler limited linewidth of 1.55 GHz for standard in-source laser spectroscopy.

With the above-described groundwork tests being successful, the ISOLDE experiment “IS664 - Investigation of octupole deformation in neutron-rich actinium using high-resolution in-source laser spectroscopy” [15], that was proposed to the ISOLDE committee within the LISA framework, became feasible. The investigations continue to pin down the area of assumed octupole deformation in the respective area of the nuclear chart by precisely determining nuclear parameters as changes in mean squared charge radii and magnetic moments, following the in-source spectroscopy work conducted at TRIUMF [11]. The experimental campaign in May 2022 was successful, yielding, e.g., first-time data on $^{230,231}\text{Ac}$ which lie exactly on the border of predicted octupole deformation. The data is currently under analysis and a publication is in preparation. Fig. 5 shows an exemplary full hyperfine structure scan on the reference isotope ^{227}Ac from this campaign – the small splitting of the ground state involved in the transition can be resolved as proposed.

Fig. 5: Schematic of the investigated transition in ^{227}Ac (taken from [11]) on the left and full scan of the hyperfine structure in PI-LIST mode from the IS664 campaign on the right. All individual components can be resolved, and the splitting of the lower state be determined.

The efficiency during this experiment was below expectations, thus a compromise on the experimental linewidth of around 400 MHz was employed. With this flexibility in settings to match the requirements for the investigated transition, the goal of the proposed experiment could be completely reached.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PLANS

The LISA deliverable 2.2, “Implementation of PI-LIST at ISOLDE”, was completed successfully. The necessary changes to the ISOLDE frontend design and laser delivery infrastructure were implemented, validated, and documented. An experimental linewidth of around 200 MHz was demonstrated at the ISOLDE GPS separator on actinium, clearly showing improved performance of the respective 1.55 GHz Doppler limit for “classical” in-source hot cavity laser spectroscopy. Due to this work, an ISOLDE on-line experiment on neutron-rich actinium isotopes to pin down the limits of assumed octupole deformation in this region of the nuclear chart became possible.

The demonstration of the PI-LIST capabilities at ISOLDE triggered various upcoming experimental programs, showing the high impact of these developments. An extension of the actinium investigation is being discussed, and laser spectroscopy activities on other actinides at ISOLDE emerging from the LISA programme will also profit from the technique [16]. An extensive campaign to investigate the lanthanide region has just been launched [17] since successful spectroscopy of these elements in the PI-LIST has already been demonstrated in Mainz. Additionally, the possibilities for enhanced isomer-selective radioactive ion beam production are requested by the ISOLDE user community, as, e.g., for decay spectroscopy investigations on cadmium isotopes following the decay of selected silver isomers [18].

High-resolution laser spectroscopy at ISOLDE and elsewhere will profit from developments on versatile and reliable narrow-bandwidth-seed (cw) and locked amplifier lasers (injection-seeded pulsed amplifier cavity), and are therefore conducted with the industrial partners in the LISA network. Enhanced spectral range capabilities will enable a wider range of accessible laser transitions, and ongoing automation and integration will allow to move the focus even more towards the actual experiment and away from binding a high fraction of expertise and manpower in the setup and maintenance of the laser systems.

Ongoing developments on the PI-LIST itself include work to overcome limitations in efficiency and contamination suppression, thus also being very beneficial to “standard” LIST operation to produce clean ion beams. On various occasions, a loss factor below the expectation was observed when switching from the standard RILIS-resembling ion guide mode of the LIST to the high purity LIST mode that is also employed for PI-LIST operation. Here, the shaping of the effusing atom beam for lower divergence is investigated by simulation and experimental work, potentially including hot cavity geometries produced by additive manufacturing (“3D printing”). Refinement of the electrical potential distribution in the LIST RFQ structure will increase the effectively accessible volume for laser ionization, while on the laser technique side repetition rate increase promises a quasi-linear scaling of efficiency. In terms of reduced purification capabilities for certain isotopes, optimized heat load management of the repeller electrodes has been identified as an approach to prevent surface ionization on these exposed parts.

Secondments at JGU Mainz and TRIUMF are planned to pursue these developments and explore the implementation possibilities of a similar high-resolution operation mode at TRIUMF’s LIST-type Ion Guide Laser Ion Source IG-LIS [19].

This report serves as an initial demonstration of the PI-LIST capabilities at ISOLDE, although, within the scope of the LISA project we plan to further characterise and develop the PI-LIST for applications to the actinides and beyond. During the remainder of the LIST project this work will continue and this report will be updated to a new version in 12 months time.

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
cw	Continuous wave
HFS	Hyperfine Structure
ISOLDE	Isotope Separation On-Line Device (RIB facility at CERN)
JGU	Johannes Gutenberg-Universität
LIST	Laser Ion Source and Trap
NB	Narrow-bandwidth
PI-LIST	Perpendicularly Illuminated Laser Ion Source and Trap
RIB	Radioactive Ion Beam
Ti:sapphire	Titanium-doped sapphire
TRIUMF	Tri-University Meson Facility (RIB facility at Vancouver, Canada)

